

The effect of plant spacing, row spacing, and nitrogen application on the yields of boro rice and of a relay crop of deep-water rice, Bangladesh.

Spacing (cm)	Boro rice yield (t/ha)		N application (kg/ha)	Deep water rice (Hbj. Aman IV) (t/ha)
	BR6	BR3		
20 × 20	3.2	5.1	0	0.3
			40	0.7
30 × 15	3.0	4.9	0	0.5
			40	1.0
15 × 15 × 49 ^a	3.0	5.0	0	0.6
			40	1.2

^a15 cm between hills and rows, 45 cm between paired rows.

seeds and reduced the plant stand.

In another study, no significant difference was found between using sprouted seeds and transplanting 30-day-old seedlings of deep-water rice. The plot was not deeply flooded, however, and deep-water rice yields averaged a respectable 1.4 t/ha.

The experiment's indicate that relay cropping of boro and deep-water rice has a definite potential for increasing rice production in some areas of Bangladesh.

But the choice of boro variety and spacing, the timing and method of planting of deep-water rice, and the amount of fertilizer needed for good stands and yields require more study. Major factors that determine the success of the cropping pattern and that vary from site to site include the timing of the flood, the moisture status during establishment of deep-water rice, and nutrient availability. ❧

Expected rice yields in rainfed systems

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The IRRI cropping systems program is investigating strategies for multiple cropping of rice in rainfed and partially

irrigated systems through appropriate choice of variety and cultural practices. Major considerations are planting dates, growth duration of rice varieties, tillage methods, planting methods (direct seeding or transplanting), and rainfall distribution. To assess farmers' yield expectations with their present

technology, yields of more than 900 farmer-managed plots of rainfed and partially irrigated rice, including 556 plots of improved and 422 plots of traditional varieties, were examined by date of harvest. The data were obtained from daily farm records kept in 1975–76 and 1976–77 by 130 farmers in Batangas, Iloilo, and Pangasinan provinces, Philippines. The times of onset and decline of bimodal rainfall patterns are similar at all the sites. The improved varieties were planted in lowland fields; most were single crops. Most traditional varieties were also single crops, but some were grown on upland fields.

The solid portions of free-hand curves in Figure 1 represent the 5-week moving averages of rice yields by week of harvest. The first peaks of the improved and traditional variety curves are the moving averages of 83 and 35 plots, respectively. The second peaks are based on 65 observations of improved varieties and 73 of traditional ones, and the intervening troughs are based on 117 and 78 observations, respectively. The lowest number of observations in any 5-week period was 22, which constitutes the moving average centered on week 33 on the improved variety curve. A maximum of 154 points are averaged for week 39, also lying on the improved variety curve. Points on the dashed portion of the improved variety curve are based on a low number of observations and mainly represent the few relatively better irrigated plots in the sample. The dashed portion of the traditional rice curve mainly represents the yields of 153 upland rice plots at the Batangas site.

While the actual rainfall pattern shifts from year to year, it generally follows a bimodal distribution with a major peak in July and a minor peak in October. We have not attempted, however, to rigorously identify possible relationships between climate and yield. The data suggest that highest total production on lowland can be expected by direct-seeding an early maturing improved variety in mid-May for harvest in early September, then transplanting a second crop for harvest in late December. Ongoing studies indicate that the availability of power and labor, and the timing of the actual onset

of rain limit farmers' opportunities to follow the high-production pattern on an entire farm. On those plots not planted by week 26, it appears advisable to plant a single, later maturing crop to harvest around the first of the year. A corroborative study in Iloilo indeed showed that in 1976 farmers shifted from early maturing varieties and direct-seeding to later maturing varieties and transplanting at about the end of June (Fig. 2).

All upland rice plots were harvested between week 34 and 41 and constitute 80% of the observations plotted on that portion of the traditional rice curve. During this period upland rice yields followed the same declining trend as yields of rainfed improved and traditional lowland rice, and compared very favorably with yields of the latter harvested in succeeding weeks. **W**

2. Area of rice planted by 46 Iloilo farmers, by week of planting, varietal maturity period, and method of planting. Iloilo province, Philippines, 1976.

Populations of parasitic nematodes of grain legumes in rice-based cropping patterns in four environments and flooding regimes in the Philippines

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Plant parasitic nematodes of the genera *Rotylenchulus* and *Meloidogyne* are important grain legume pests in the Philippines. Those genera do not attack graminaceous crops such as rice and corn in rice cropping patterns. A study was undertaken at the target area of the IRRI-Bureau of Plant Industry Cropping Systems Program in Manaog, Pangasinan, Philippines, to determine the nematode incidence in four common rice-growing environments, each distinguished by duration of flooding:

1. well-drained, nonpuddled fields planted to upland rice (nonflooded);
2. isolated rice paddies in drainageways among upland fields, where a crop of transplanted rice is flooded from 2 to 3 months during the rainy season;

Plant parasitic nematode populations in mung beans and cowpeas following rice in four environments.^a Pangasinan, Philippines, 1976.

Environment	Nematodes (no./250 cc soil and 1 g roots)		
	<i>Rotylenchulus</i>	<i>Meloidogyne</i>	Total of 7 genera ^b
Upland fields	56	431	551
Isolated paddies in drainageways among upland fields	2	0	17
Highly intermittently flooded fields	2	5	35
Normal rainfed paddies	1	0	3

^aAv. of 4 fields in each environmental condition having a similar cropping pattern during the previous 3 years.

^b*Criconemoides, Helicotylenchus, Hoplolaimus, Pratylenchus, Tylenchorhynchus.*

3. paddies in lowland areas of alkaline soil that are flooded highly intermittently. Alternate flooding (no more than 1–2 weeks) and draining of such paddies alleviates iron and zinc deficiencies; and

4. normal lowland rainfed paddies with good water retention during rice cultivation (flooded for 2–3 months).

Soil and root samples were taken from mung beans or cowpeas planted after the single rice crop in four replicated fields for each environment. Soil samples from each field were pooled and nematodes

were extracted by the Baermann funnel technique. Roots were stained with acid fuchsin-lactophenol and examined under a microscope.

The results indicated that flooding during rice culture, even intermittently, is an effective cultural method for controlling plant parasitic nematodes (see table). Only in the well-drained, nonflooded, upland environment did we find very high nematode populations capable of reducing yields of legumes planted after rice. **W**